

INCIDENCE OF REPUTATIONAL PERIODICITY

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Abstract. *Reputation time series are analysed for periodic affects which might not be visible using simple smoothing techniques. To find possible frequencies that might indicate periodicity, a bandpass filter with a narrow passband, wide stopbands and steep roll-offs is progressively tracked on a day-by-day basis across reputation time series spanning a two-year period. Dominant frequencies are recorded at each stage. The results indicate that periodic cycles exist in the general range of one to six months. This result is significant for reputation management because it indicates when upturns or downturns in reputation are most likely.*

1 INTRODUCTION

Reputation may be formulated as time series of numeric sentiment values [1], in which total sentiment with respect to a given organisation is harvested and scored numerically on a daily basis using *Natural Language processing* and increasingly, *Large Language Models*. The purpose of this study is to examine the extent of periodic effects within reputation time series. An estimate of the period of an organisation’s reputation is of benefit because it may reveal persistent failures in reputational management.

The illustration in Figure 1 shows a typical reputation time series: *Apple Corp.*. It has the characteristic rapid sentiment reversals, with some evidence of periodicity, as judged by inter-peak (or inter-tough) distances.

Figure 1: Example of reputation series: Apple Corp., illustrating rapid sentiment reversal and tentative evidence of periodicity. Red trace: empirical data, blue trace: Loess smoothed. Date range 730 days, July 2021-June 2023. Data: *Penta Group*.

1.1 Bandpass Filtration Applied to Reputation

The proposed method for searching for periodic effects in reputation time series is to construct and apply a bandpass filter to the data, as a means to assess the significance of frequency components embedded in the input data. A bandpass filter serves to transmit only frequencies that fall within a certain range (determined by the way in which the filter is structured), whilst minimising frequencies that fall outside that range. The amplitude of the transmitted signal is then a measure of the significance of the transmitted frequency. To apply the method, a bandpass filter is applied at each point defined by the time series. In the context of reputation the points are defined by *days*. The following sequence summarises the principal stages for a single reputation time series.

1. Filter design
2. For each day, t within scope of the data:
 - (a) Formulate a bandpass filter based on t

- (b) Apply the filter to all days and calculate significance for day t
3. Model the significance profile by a high degree polynomial, P
4. Locate turning points on P
5. Estimate significant frequencies from the highest three peaks

2 TECHNICAL BACKGROUND

2.1 Data and Implementation

Reputation time series from July 2021 to June 2023 for 130 corporate organisations were sourced from *Penta Group*¹. Each element in the data series for organisation T represents the collective sentiment of all comments expressed for T on a given day. In the *Penta* implementation, daily sentiments are recorded on a scale from -100 (the worst possible) to +100 (the best possible).

The implementation is entirely in *Mathematica* (version 13.3), which allows seamless integration of numeric, symbolic and graphical methods. In particular, the calculus constructs in Section 4 provide the key to period determination.

2.2 Bandpass Filtration

Bandpass filters are used in a variety of applications, such as radios, TVs, and cell phones. They can be used to remove unwanted signals, such as noise, from a signal, or to select a particular range of frequencies for processing. High bandpass filters are used in audio systems to remove low-frequency noise, such as hum. Low bandpass filters are used in telephone systems to remove high-frequency noise, such as hiss.

Frequency filters can, in general, be represented by *frequency response curves* which are plots of standardised frequency (the independent variable) against amplitude (or a simple function thereof, the dependent variable). Figure 2 shows the bandpass profile, the parameters that are needed to characterise it, and derived parameters.

The principal inputs parameters for filter design are listed below. The output for filter design is an amplitude $|H(f)|^2$, dependent on frequency f .

1. f_{pa} : the lower passband frequency; f_{pb} : the upper passband frequency.
2. f_{sa} : the lower stopband frequency; f_{sb} : the upper stopband frequency.
3. f_s : the Nyquist (scaling) frequency
4. A_p : the stopband attenuation; A_s : the passband attenuations.

¹<https://pentagroup.co>

Figure 2: Bandpass filter response characteristics and parameters

The attenuations (i.e. reductions in amplitude) characterise the 'rectangular' nature of the filter profile. The terms e_p and e_s are derived quantities given A_p and A_s , although it more convenient to use them as the primary inputs for the filter design. In Figure 2, f_c is the mean of f_{pa} and f_{pb} if the filter is symmetric (the simplest case). The attenuations in the regions (f_{sa}, f_{sa}) and (f_{pb}, f_{sb}) are known as *roll-offs*.

3 SUPPORTING LITERATURE

This review illustrates instances of filter design and usage for particular purposes. The use of filters in the context of reputation is, aside from this paper, unexplored.

Radio, Radar and Transmission

A general overview of the use of bandpass filters in radio frequency applications may be found in [5]. They include telecoms, in which transmission by fibre networks is important, spectroscopy to block unwanted light scattering, LiDAR, and satellite communications. Recent specific applications include Sekiya et al [6] - the design of an array of single-band bandpass filters for radio astronomy in the UHF band, and Horlbeck et al. [10] - an adjustable bandpass filter for passive radar. Zamuruev et al [11] provide an overview of the main types of radio-frequency filters in radio-frequency systems. Radio-based applications frequently describe physical devices that include bandpass filters. Examples include Wu et al. [7] - for multi-band radio transmission; Xiang et al [8] - for designing a filter that allows a substantial tuning range of operational frequencies, and Durganath and Raja [9] - a delay filter. Further examples are Kiouach et al. [12] and Le et al. [13].

Audio

Ganguly et al. describe a study of speech signal distortion in audio systems, and attempt to filter out as much amplitude and frequency distortion as possible. They demonstrate that phase distortion is normally inaudible to the human ear. Yang et al. [15] designed an adjustable bandpass filter that is connected to a portable audio device such as an

mp3 player. Similarly, Wang et al. [16] describe a physical bandpass filter for 6G mobile communication.

Business and economics

Harvey and Trimbur [4] used bandpass filters to extract business cycles in economic time series. They point out that economic data usually have distinct statistical properties compared to data derived from physical systems (such as in electrical engineering). Typically, the 'sharp-gain' filters used in electronics can cause distortions in economic contexts that make the filter output extremely misleading. They cite the case of 'finding' cycles (which do not really exist) using a 'sharp-gain' filter on white noise, and give stock price changes as an example. However, stock price changes (and reputation) are not white noise. Rather, they are highly auto-correlated. The result from such economic series is a response variability which might not be present in physical systems.

4 IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

The purpose of the bandpass filtration is to isolate successive narrow frequency bands, and determine which of them are most significant. The principal steps were noted in Section 1.1.

4.1 Filter Design

The designing needs for filtering a narrow bandpass filter 'rectangular-like': high roll-off (i.e. high attenuation), at the expense of signal attenuation within the pass band. This can be a problem in physical systems, but is less so in economic (including reputation) contexts. the passband limits f_{pa} and f_{pb} is best defined by starting with the central frequency f_c and defining the passband semi-width w , so that $f_{pa} = f_c - w$ and $f_{pb} = f_c + w$. Following the method noted by Orfanidis [2] (section 11.6.5 and 11.6.1), the stages in designing a filter with the characteristic profile in Figure 2 are as follows.

Step 1 : Scaling to frequency range $[0, 2\pi]$.

$$\begin{aligned}\omega_{pa} &= \frac{2\pi f_{pa}}{f_s}; & \omega_{pb} &= \frac{2\pi f_{pb}}{f_s} \\ \omega_{sa} &= \frac{2\pi f_{sa}}{f_s}; & \omega_{sb} &= \frac{2\pi f_{sb}}{f_s}\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

Step 2 : Analogue Frequency Mappings (c measures the amplitude ratios in Figure 2)
 Ω_p and Ω_s are the analogue 'pass' and 'stop' frequencies respectively.

$$\begin{aligned}
 c &= \frac{\sin(\omega_{pa} + \omega_{pb})}{\sin(\omega_{pa}) + \sin(\omega_{pb})} \\
 \Omega_p &= \left| \frac{c - \cos(\omega_{pb})}{\sin(\omega_{pb})} \right| \\
 \Omega_{sa} &= \frac{c - \cos(\omega_{sa})}{\sin(\omega_{sa})}; \quad \Omega_{sb} = \frac{c - \cos(\omega_{sb})}{\sin(\omega_{sb})} \\
 \Omega_s &= \min(|\Omega_{sa}|, |\Omega_{sb}|)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Step 3 : Butterworth Frequency parameters calculation. N_{exact} and its rounded up version N refer to the filter order and Ω_0 is the normalization frequency.

$$N_{exact} = \left\lceil \frac{\log\left(\frac{e_s}{e_p}\right)}{\log\left(\frac{\Omega_s}{\Omega_p}\right)} \right\rceil; \quad N = \lceil N_{exact} \rceil; \quad \Omega_0 = \frac{\Omega_p}{e_p^{1/N}} \tag{3}$$

Step 4 : Magnitude Response calculation. The output is a single response magnitude, which describes filter profile (as in Figure 2) for a single input frequency f . The other inputs are c (Step 2), N and Ω_0 (Step 3), and the Nyquist (scaling) frequency f_s . The output is the response $|H(f)|^2$ in Figure 2.

$$\omega = \frac{2\pi f}{f_s}; \quad \Omega = \frac{c - \cos[\omega]}{\sin(\omega)}; \quad |H(f)|^2 = \left(1 + \left(\frac{\Omega}{\Omega_0}\right)^{2N}\right)^{-1} \tag{4}$$

Steps 1-3 can be summarised in a function $\mathcal{B}()$, which is a constructor for a generic Bandpass filter, appropriate for reputational analysis. Equation 5 shows the inputs and outputs.

$$\{\Omega_0, c, N\} = \mathcal{B}(f_{pa}, f_{pb}, f_{sa}, f_{sb}, f_s, e_p, e_s) \tag{5}$$

A second function \mathcal{H} (Equation 6), summarises the magnitude response calculation at a particular frequency f_t (Step 4). Since f_t is identified by a day number, it can take any integer value from 1 to the Nyquist frequency number $\lfloor f_s/2 \rfloor$. The output is a single real number h_t . The output feeds into the next stage in the process, which is to apply the filter to data.

$$h_t = \mathcal{H}(f_t, \Omega_0, c, N, f_s) \tag{6}$$

Some examples of filter construction are shown in Section 5.1.

4.2 The Bandpass Filter applied to data

To apply \mathcal{H} to the entire reputation time series y_t ; ($t = 1..f_s$), a vector of target frequencies $f_1, f_2, \dots, f_{\lfloor f_s/2 \rfloor}$ must be defined, and the corresponding values of h_t calculated. The reputation data y_t must be restricted to the corresponding instances of f_t (i.e. up to the

Nyquist frequency). Series f_t and the restricted y_t are then multiplied pairwise, and a root mean square of the products produces a single real-valued positive response R_t at frequency f_t .

$$\begin{aligned}
 \{h_t\} &= \{\mathcal{H}(f_t, \Omega_0, c, N, f_s)\}; \quad t = 1.. \lfloor f_s/2 \rfloor \\
 \{y'_t\} &= \{f_t h_t\} \quad t = 1.. \lfloor f_s/2 \rfloor \\
 R_t &= \left(\sum_{t=1}^{\lfloor f_s/2 \rfloor} (y'_t)^2 \right)^{1/2}
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

The sequence in Equations 7 can be summarised in a single function \mathcal{R} (Equation 8). With integer values for the 'target' frequencies f_t , the values of f_t reduce to integers $1.. \lfloor f_s/2 \rfloor$. The output R_t is a measure of the significance of the input frequency f_t on the data.

$$R_t = \mathcal{R}(f_t, y_t, \Omega_0, c, N, f_s); \quad t = 1.. \lfloor f_s/2 \rfloor \tag{8}$$

To see the effect of all frequencies on the data, function \mathcal{R} has to be applied at frequencies between 1 and the Nyquist number, $\lfloor f_s/2 \rfloor$. The first frequency $f_{t_1} (> 1)$ must be high enough to accommodate the profile of a bandpass filter. Similarly, the last frequency $f_{t_2} (\leq \lfloor f_s/2 \rfloor)$ must be low enough to accommodate the same profile. A value for each R_t in the range $[f_{t_1}..f_{t_2}]$ then needs to be calculated. Algorithm 1 returns a sequence of R_t -values.

Algorithm 1 : Frequency significance calculation.

1. Determine start and end frequencies f_{t_1} and f_{t_2} .
2. For each frequency f_t in $[f_{t_1}..f_{t_2}]$:
 - (a) $\{\Omega_0, c, N\} = \mathcal{B}(f_{pa}, f_{pb}, f_{sa}, f_{sb}, f_s, e_p, e_s)$
 - (b) $h_t = \mathcal{H}(f_t, \Omega_0, c, N, f_s)$
 - (c) $R_t = \mathcal{R}(f_t, y_t, \Omega_0, c, N, f_s)$
3. Return $\{R_t\}$

When Algorithm 1 is embedded in a single procedure \mathcal{S} , the necessary inputs are the parameters needed to construct the bandpass filter, the reputation time series, and the start and end frequencies (Equation 9). The output is a list of frequency significance

values $\{R_t\}$ that defines a significance profile for the reputation data y_t . An example plot of $\{R_t\}$ against frequencies f_t is shown in Section 5.2.

$$\{R_t\} = \mathcal{S}(f_{pa}, f_{pb}, f_{sa}, f_{sb}, f_s, e_p, e_s, y_t, f_{t_1}, f_{t_2}) \quad (9)$$

4.3 Period Estimation

The result of applying function \mathcal{S} (Equation 9) is a list of peak frequencies. Typically, for any given organisation, they will not be numerous, and inter-peak distances may vary significantly. Therefore, estimation of a period will be associated with much uncertainty. With those provisos, Algorithm 2 shows the period estimation details. The key part is to express the frequency significance profile $\{R_t\}$ into a continuous form that can be differentiated in order to locate maxima (or minima).

Algorithm 2 : Period Estimation.

1. Fit a high degree polynomial, $P(f)$, to the frequency significance profile $\{R_t\}$
2. Calculate $\frac{dP}{df}$ and $\frac{d^2P}{df^2}$
3. Solve $\frac{dP}{df} = 0$ to give solutions $\{f_1, f_2, \dots\}$ subject to $\frac{d^2P}{df^2}|_{f_i} < 0$ to detect the maxima
4. Remove negative f_i
5. Extract the maximum 3 f_i , and order by frequency

The result of applying Algorithm 2 is, for each organisation, a triple of the most significant frequencies. Ordering them by frequency is useful for visualisation (Section 5.3). Less reliance should be placed on results that indicate a very high number of days. It would be hard to observe high value periodic effects given the number of days spanned by the data (730) because a consistent pattern cannot be established. Therefore, a nominal upper limit for reportable frequency of a quarter of the number of data data points ($f_s/4$ in Figure 2) is set.

5 RESULTS

5.1 Bandpass filter examples

Figure 3 shows three Bandpass filter examples generated using the sequence in Section 4. They illustrate the idealised profile in Figure 2. Two are centred on the same frequency,

24 (i.e. day 24), with a nominal 3 month span $f_s = 90$. The third is centred at 20. In each case the pass band semi-width is w . The roll-offs are controlled by parameters e_s and e_p : increasing e_s and decreasing e_p produces a steeper roll-off.

- **Red:** $e_p = 0.5, e_s = 2, f_{pa} = 20; f_{pb} = 28; w = 5$
- **Blue:** $e_p = 0.3493, e_s = 3, f_{pa} = 23; f_{pb} = 25; w = 1$
- **Green:** $e_p = 0.05, e_s = 12, f_{pa} = 12; f_{pb} = 28; w = 8$

Figure 3: Examples of Bandpass filters. Red: wide pass band, shallow roll-off. Blue: narrow pass band, steep roll-off. Green: very wide pass band, almost vertical roll-off.

5.2 Single Reputation Example

This section shows an example frequency calculation for *Tesco* using Algorithm 2 (Section 4.3). The plot in Figure 4 shows the trace of frequency significance for frequencies between 1 to 270 days. The bandpass region was set at a very small value: 4 days. Parameters e_p and e_s (in Figure 2) were set to $1/3$ and 3 respectively to give a very wide with steep roll-off on either side of the passband region. In this case the three principal frequency peaks are closely packed and have very similar significance values. Each marks a peak in a region of significance. The fourth highest, 236 days, falls outside the nominal upper limit for reportable frequency number (Section 4.3), so that value would be hard to justify without recourse to more data. The fifth highest peak, at 5 days, is also hard to justify because it falls within the range of 'noise'. The sixth highest peak, 184 days, is on the boundary of the 'justifiable' region. In this case the Loess approximation has smoothed several minor peaks in the range 140-200, so that the 184-day peak can be regarded as an average for that region.

5.3 All Reputation Results

The results of applying Algorithm 2 to the reputation data of all organisations reveals a consistent pattern. There is some periodic effect for each organisation, and it is usually possible to identify three peaks (including the global maximum) in the frequency profile.

Figure 4: Example of Significant Periods analysis: Tesco, showing the three most significant peaks at 33, 62 and 100 days. Red - Significance profile from $\mathcal{S}()$ (Equation 9). Blue - Loess peaks model (Algorithm 2).

None had fewer than two. For those that had more than three identifiable peaks, peaks 4, 5, ... were insignificant compared to the three principal frequency peaks. Figure 5 shows histograms of the three principal frequencies, all based on a fitting a polynomial of degree 25 to the frequency profiles. Summary statistics corresponding to Figure 5, using a passband width 4, are shown in Table 1 (MAD = *Mean Absolute Deviation*). The figure 25 for degree provided a faithful representation of the frequency profile, whilst removing minor variations. A passband width of 4 is a reasonable wrap around a single target frequency, whilst allowing a small amount of stability from neighbouring frequencies. Both table and histogram indicate frequency peaks in the region of 1-2 months, 3 months and 5-6 months, all with a wide estimation margin.

Figure 5: Significant frequencies (in days): all organisations, showing profiles for short, medium and long term periodic effects

5.3.1 Bandpass filter with a shallow roll-off

It is interesting to compare the results of Section 5.3 with corresponding results using an alternative bandpass filter. Noting the advice from Harvey and Trimbur [4] that a

Table 1: Summary statistics of peaks of frequency profiles, all organisations

Statistic	Frequency (days)		
	Lower	Medium	Upper
Mean	41	88	141
SD	22.9	26.3	34.1
Max	231	156	229
Min	21	48	79
Median	37	83	138.5
MAD	21.9	26.8	28.2

Table 2: Summary statistics of peaks of frequency profiles, all organisations, using a 'wide' bandpass filter with a short pass band and shallow roll-offs.

Statistic	Frequency (days)		
	Lower	Medium	Upper
Mean	40	89	141
SD	17.8	28.4	35.8
Max	134	218	258
Min	21	48	79
Median	37	83	138
MAD	22.7	28.0	27.2

bandpass filter with a very sharp roll-off may give misleading results, a bandpass filter with a very shallow roll-off is investigated in this section. Figure 3 shows such a filter (in red), although for consistency with the setup for Section 5.3, the pass band is kept very narrow, at 4 days. Increasing the value of the e_p parameter from 0.3 to 0.5, and decreasing the e_s parameter from 3.0 to 1.0 resulted in roll-offs of approximately 14 days (they were approximately 2 days). With no other changes, Table 2 shows the equivalent statistics for 'wide' filter to those in Table 1. The results for the 'wide' filter are very similar to the results for the original filter.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Using a bandpass filter has revealed 'hidden' periodicity in reputation time series. It should be remembered that the figures given in Section 5.3 (1-6 months) are guidelines, and they should be treated as such. Those involved in risk management should adopt a strategy of continuous monitoring of reputation, and be aware that at approximately 1, 3 and 6 months, there may be an upturn or a downturn in sentiment.

Within an individual calculation, some improvements are possible. The degree of the

polynomial use to model the frequency distribution (Algorithm 2) does not have a theoretical basis. Rather, the only proviso is that the degree should be large enough to model the major features of the frequency profile adequately. Varying the polynomial degree can produce anomalous results, particularly if additional low frequency peaks are detected. This phenomenon does not appear to be due to even or odd numbered degrees. In any single organisation, it is mostly easy to deal with this problem. The list of significant frequencies for each polynomial degree should be scrutinised manually, and outlier degrees should be rejected. An example is for *Astra Zeneca* where the lowest frequencies with pass band width 6 for polynomial degrees 20-30 are {29, 27, 28, 29, 35, 34, 66, 65, 34, 35, 35}, and two outliers are apparent. Averages can then be calculated for the remainder. Ideally, searching for outliers should be done programmatically, but outlier identification is not always clear in this context. For example, there are cases (such as IBM, British Aerospace or United Healthcare) where the lower significant frequency values fall into two widely-separated clusters, with approximately half in each. For *IBM*, the corresponding lowest frequencies with pass band width 15 are {87, 87, 87, 87, 87, 87, 87, 87, 31, 31, 29}. In that case, the issue could be resolved by averaging or by a majority decision. The problem is much more acute for wider pass bands.

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